

FEEDBACK QUESTIONNAIRE – PARTICIPANTS - PRE

Please answer the following questions about your knowledge about statistics, big data and professional profiles now. The questions are answered by answering from 0 to 4, being '0'=Not at all and '4' a lot. The survey is anonymous and there are no right or wrong answers.

STATISTICS AND BIG DATA

ITEM	0 Not at all	1	2	3	4 A lot
Do you know the difference between statistics and big data?					
How important is Statistics in your daily life?					
How important is Big Data in your daily life?					
Do you have prior knowledge of Statistics and/or Big Data?					
Have you ever had to use tools or knowledge related to Statistics and/or Big Data?					

What degree of knowledge do you possess with regards to the following skills?	0 Very low	1	2	3	4 Very high
Data Architect: create secure databases					
Engineer: to process and scale data					
Analyst: extract statistical descriptives and basic information from databases					
Scientist: to create complex statistical models					
Statistician: Narrate and interpret data and results and draw conclusions					
Data Entrepreneur: Generate business strategies through data					

FEEDBACK QUESTIONNAIRE – PARTICIPANTS - POST

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STATISTICS AND BIG DATA

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Engineer: to process and scale data					
Analyst: extract statistical descriptives and basic information from databases					
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Statistician: Narrate and interpret data and results and draw conclusions					
Data Entrepreneur: Generate business strategies through data					

Please answer the following questions about your satisfaction with the activity

ITEM	0 Very unsatisfied	1 Unsatisfied	2 Neutral	3 Satisfied	4 Very satisfied
Overall satisfaction with the activity					
Satisfaction with the information/practice received and shared					
Satisfaction with the dynamics used					
User experience with the educational game					
Satisfaction with the organisation/logistics					
Do you consider that you have learned what the activity sought to promote?					

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